

DIGITAL ULTRASONIC NDE FOR COMPOSITES THROUGH COMPLETE WAVEFORM ACQUISITION

Roberto Teti

(Department of Materials and Production Engineering, University of Naples, P.le Tecchio 80, 80125 - Napoli, Italy)

ABSTRACT

Ultrasonic (UT) non-destructive evaluation (NDE) of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates was carried out using a complete waveform digital acquisition and analysis technique. The CFRP laminates were fabricated with different autoclave cycles and their geometrical, structural, and mechanical properties were destructively evaluated. A correlation between these results and UT NDE data was sought to nondestructively discriminate the laminates quality levels, with particular reference to porosity content and its influence on composite mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Ultrasonic (UT) non-destructive evaluation (NDE) of composites has been shown capable of characterizing defects and structural properties that critically influence the material mechanical behavior [1-3]. The scopes of the present research activity are the evaluation of the consequences of autoclave fabrication cycle variations on carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates geometry, structure and mechanical properties, and the correlation of mechanical properties, structural characteristics and UT NDE data, obtained from CFRP laminates. UT NDE was carried out using a complete waveform digital acquisition and analysis technique [4-6]. In this case, a volumetric UT database is formed, from which information on any thickness portion of the material can be obtained. The eventual goal of the program is the realization and optimization of an automated ultrasonic NDE expert system capable of identifying defective conditions in FRP composites and predicting their criticality during service.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Four quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with stacking sequence $(0_2/\pm 45_2/90_2)_2s$ and nominal thickness 4 mm were fabricated by a different autoclave cycle for each laminate type, identified as A, B, C, and D (Table 1).

Table 1 - Fabrication cycle variations

Laminate Id	Autoclave cycle
A	Very few bleeder layers
B	Very few bleeder layers, no vacuum applied
C	Fewer bleeder layers than standard cycle
D	Standard cycle

Autoclave cycle differences were expected to determine variations in thickness, fiber/resin fraction, porosity content, and mechanical properties of the laminates. Pulse-echo ultrasonic C-scans were carried out on samples obtained from the four laminate types. Their maximum size was approximately 100 x 50 mm. A mechanical immersion scanner was used for the motioning of a focused broadband 20 MHz immersion transducer. The increment between consecutive scan lines (step) was 0.5 mm. After interaction of the ultrasound with the material, the detected RF waveform was digitized by a 125 MHz digital oscilloscope at 100 MHz sampling rate in order to fulfill the Nyquist criteria. The digitized complete UT waveforms were then transmitted to an advanced graphic workstation. Information regarding transducer position was also available in order to create a complete waveform database. UT databases were stored on hard disk and their size was in the range of 6 - 9 MB, according to scan size. The analysis of the UT data files allows for software generation and enhancement of images referring to any portion of laminate thickness [4]. Images were presented on screen and photographed through a hardcopier.

Geometrical and structural examinations, comprising thickness measurement, fiber volume fraction determination, micrographic examinations and porosity content evaluation, were carried out. Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) was chosen for mechanical characterization, because of its sensitivity to porosity content [7-9].

RESULTS

1. Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS)

ILSS was evaluated through three-point bending of short beam samples, according to ASTM D2344-84. A dispersion parameter, d , given by the ratio between standard deviation and mean value was calculated. From each laminate type 12 to 15 samples were tested and the results are summarized in Table 2. ILSS varies between a rather low (46 N/mm^2) and a satisfactory value for this type of material (86 N/mm^2) [9], according to the autoclave cycle. Dispersion values are rather small and were judged acceptable.

Table 2 - Experimental results

Id	ILSS		Thickness (mm)	V_f		V_p		RRS
	Mean (N/mm^2)	Disp. (%)		Mean (%)	Disp. (%)	Mean (%)	Disp. (%)	
A	57	11	4.9	50	7	1.15	38	Medium
B	46	9	5.3	49	10	2.05	40	High
C	71	10	4.1	59	5	0.85	35	-
D	86	8	4.1	63	5	-	-	-

ILSS = interlaminar shear strength; V_f = fiber volume fraction; V_p = porosity content; RRS = resin rich areas size

2. Geometrical measurements and micrographic examinations

The average thickness of the four laminate types was measured and reported in Table 2; he observed dispersion was very low and is not reported. Samples of the four laminate types were subjected to micrographic examinations after completion of the complete waveform C-scanning. Photomicrographs at 50x, covering the entire sample section, were used to reconstruct a "collaged" micrographic image.

The collages were utilized for micrographic examinations of fiber volume fraction, fiber distribution, resin rich areas presence, void content, size and distribution. Qualitative considerations on the above properties were also made on the basis of such examinations (Table 2).

3. Fiber volume fraction

Fiber volume fraction was determined from photomicrographs by evaluating total area of fibers in a given area of the micrograph both through a quantitative image analyzer and by counting the number of fibers in the area and calculating the total fiber area from their average diameter. The fiber volume fraction was calculated as $V_f = A_f/A$, where A_f and A are the total fiber area and the area of the selected region of the micrograph, respectively. The results are shown in Table 2 where mean values and dispersion parameters are reported for each laminate type.

5. Porosity content measurements

Porosity content was measured through micrographic examinations and a photomicrographic technique: the total area of the porosities present in a given area of the micrograph was determined directly with a quantitative image analyzer. The porosity content was determined as $V_p = A_p/A$, where A_p and A are the total porosity area and the area of the selected region of the micrograph, respectively. The obtained results are shown in Table 2 where both mean values and dispersion parameters are reported for each laminate type.

5. Resin rich areas

The presence and size of local resin rich areas were qualitatively evaluated through micrographic examinations. Resin rich areas are generally located between layers, although sometimes are also found within a single layer. The results of such examinations are summarized in Table 2.

6. Ultrasonic testing

In Figs. 1A to D the images and typical waveforms of the scanned samples are shown. For each figure, four images are displayed; the four images were obtained, after the scanning operation, by setting via software four different gates on the typical UT waveform of the laminate, so that four successive portions of the laminate thickness were examined. The typical waveforms in Fig. 1 refer to the arrow locations and the time gates, corresponding to the images containing the arrows, are indicated by vertical bars. The images of each sample correspond to four material portions; as the laminates contained 32 layers, each portion represents ~ 8 layers (~ 1.2 mm). It is possible to exploit this technique till the interfaces between the single laminae of the composite can be monitored utilizing the UT data file obtained from a single scan. In Fig. 2 an example is given of 32 images representing 32 different portions of a 32-layers D sample.

Fig. 1 - UT images and typical waveforms from samples A, B, C, D. For each sample four images from four different gates are displayed. The waveforms refer to the arrow positions on the corresponding images.

Fig. 2 - 32 UT images from a 32-layers D sample.

DISCUSSION

1. Structural and mechanical properties

Mechanical tests and structural examinations evidenced two basic quality levels in the four laminate types. Laminates A and B display a very low quality whereas laminates C and D show a rather high quality. The former laminates are characterized by a very low ILSS, high actual thickness, low fiber fraction, high porosity content and size, and presence of resin rich areas (Table 2). The low ILSS may be attributed to the negative influence of porosity. Fig. 3 shows that ILSS reduction with increasing porosity is approximately linear, as also observed in [8] for carbon/epoxy composites with porosity in the range 0 - 6% by volume.

Fig. 3 - ILSS vs. porosity content.

The high actual thickness, low fiber fraction and presence of resin rich areas are due to a high resin content, consequence of insufficient bleeder layers during fabrication (Table 1). The high porosity content and size come from non-expulsion of excess resin and the absence of vacuum application during fabrication (Table 1).

Laminates C and D, on the contrary, are characterized by a high ILSS, an actual thickness practically coincident with the nominal one, a high fiber fraction, a low

or negligible porosity content and no resin rich areas (Table 2). Autoclave cycles close to standard requirements account for the good properties of these laminates. It also seems possible to discriminate between laminates within the same quality group. In the low quality group, laminate A has a lower actual thickness, a slightly higher fiber fraction and a lower resin rich areas average size than laminate B. Its porosity content is significantly lower and, accordingly, its ILSS higher than for laminate B. In the high quality group, the only structural difference is the higher porosity content of laminate C in comparison with the negligible porosity content of laminate D (Table 2). ILSS is accordingly higher for laminate D, confirming its high sensitivity to porosity content above all other structural condition [10].

2. Ultrasonic evaluation

From the images in Figs. 1A to 1D, it may be noticed that samples A and B contain diffuse porosities, some of which of large size. Sample C also displays diffuse porosities but no large one and porosity average size is much lower than for samples A and B. Finally, images from sample D do not evidence significant porosity.

Laminates thickness differences can also be observed by measuring the time distance between front and back echo of the UT waveforms displayed in the grid in each figure. Defects like large porosities are clearly shown in the images as dark spots; when the correspondent UT waveform is retrieved from the database through a mouse command, a significant peak is observed in the waveform within the corresponding gate, as shown as an example in Fig. 1B. An additional way to carry out this type of point examination is to perform the FFT of the selected waveform. As shown in Fig. 4, a good material zone and a porosity defect yield significantly different FFTs: both display two main peaks at ~ 6 MHz and ~ 18 MHz, but in the case of good material the higher frequency peak has a much lower amplitude than in the porosity case.

Fig. 4 - FFTs from sample B: (a) good material, (b) porosity defect shown in Fig. 1B.

Information on the difference in attenuation induced in ultrasound by the four laminate types can be obtained from the back echo amplitude in the UT waveforms. A higher porosity laminate determines a higher scattering of UT energy within the material; accordingly, the back echo amplitude is lower than for lower porosity laminate. Back echo amplitude is a measure of UT attenuation

and may consequently be used as a quantitative measure of porosity content [11-12].

A further means to investigate the laminate global properties, including porosity content, is represented by the statistical analysis of the complete waveform database. To survey the statistical properties of the UT database three-dimensional histograms may be used. A 3-D histogram is formed by color coding the number of occurrences of waveform values in the UT database proportionally to the deviation from a reference (mode) waveform [12]. Histograms examination allows for an immediate identification of possible defective conditions on the basis of the standard deviation of all the UT waveforms from the reference and the amplitude of the back echo. In Fig. 5, the 3-D histograms of the four laminate types are reported. A variation of grey tones may be observed in the histograms: the lighter the tone, the higher the deviation from the reference waveform.

Fig. 5 - UT database three-dimensional histograms of samples A, B, C, and D.

It may be noted that the A and B laminates (Figs. 5a and b) display a higher distance between front and back echo than laminates C and D (Figs. 5c and d), indicating their higher actual thickness; moreover, laminate A displays a higher back echo than laminate B, witnessing a higher scattering of UT energy due to its higher porosity content. Laminates C and D (Figs. 5c and d) display a rather high back echo, consequence of low porosity; laminate D has the highest back echo, attributable to its negligible porosity. Laminates C and D also display a rather low data deviation, especially in the first part of the histogram near the front echo.

CONCLUSIONS

The observations on the quality levels of CFRP laminates fabricated with different autoclave cycles, made on the basis of UT NDE data, have been found in agreement with the results of the destructive evaluation of the laminates structural and mechanical properties. The complete waveform digital acquisition technique offers, through statistical processing of the complete waveform

database, parameters capable of identifying the global properties of the material, without resorting to subjective procedures of image analysis. To proceed towards the implementation of an automated UT-NDE expert system, though, more quantitative information is needed; volumetric UT databases seem to be an excellent source for the extraction and utilization of such intelligence.

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